

**USE ROTATIONAL EXERCISES TO DEVELOP SPEED
ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ КРУГОВЫХ ТРЕНИРОВОК ДЛЯ РАЗВИТИЯ
СКОРОСТИ**

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Annotation

The article explains how to create special exercises for speeding up school students in physical education classes. As well as the choice of tools in the course of the circular exercises in developing students' speed of movement, critical and sensory cycles as well as the development of movement speed using various tests.

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается вопрос методики организации специальных занятий на уроках физической культуры для развития быстроты двигательных действий школьников. А также, выбор средств, упражнений и различных тестов с учетом сенситивного и критического периода школьников при развитии быстроты двигательных действий и системы движений в процессе круговой тренировки.

Key words

School education process, physical education lesson, sensory period, circular training method, activity, speed of movement, pedagogical process.

Ключевые слова

Учебный процесс в школе, урок физического воспитания, сенсетивный период, метод круговой тренировки, активность движений, быстрота движений, педагогический процесс.

Relevance. Physical culture and sports should become an integral part of the common culture of every citizen living in our country. At the current stage of development of humane society, in the field of physical culture and sports, issues related to improving the general level of physical fitness and development of motor skills of schoolchildren, popularization of physical culture and sports, selection as a reserve for big sports are especially relevant. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev dated January 24, 2020 No. 245924-PF "On measures for further development and popularization of physical culture and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" serves as a basis and regulations in this area. -allows sorting of normative documents (2).

The educational process in general education schools involves the creation of the basis for basic physical training, the formation of the necessary reserve of movement, skills and abilities in students, their harmonious development in all respects. Research into more effective ways to improve motor skills will help to improve the physical education of schoolchildren. There are "critical or sensory" periods in the development of motor activities, during which it is proved that targeted action has the most positive changes in children's motor skills and physical development. 'p research suggests that if these periods are not used, the improvement of physical abilities may not take place at all or may be with great difficulty and adaptation. Currently, due to the limited number of hours of physical education

classes in the school curriculum (2 academic hours per week), it is not possible to introduce daily physical education classes. recommend the maximum use of periods that promote the targeted development of certain physical qualities for the development of flour. This is especially true for children between the ages of 7 and 9-10. Therefore, it is important to monitor their accuracy during exercise and movement activities. During this period, children's ability to absorb the selective effects of specially selected exercises increases (3,4).

One of the most important challenges in the physical education of the younger generation is to find effective tools and methods to help children develop motor skills. Accordingly, the need for research aimed at developing a methodology for developing the speed of movement that is manifested in exercise, which forms the basis of the physical education program with young school-age children, has become even more urgent: using their results, it will be possible to ensure the rapid development of this physical quality in the most favorable period. It was found that targeted exposure was most effective only when it coincided with favorable periods in the development of motor activity (3,5,6), and that the rapid development of agility as a motor activity occurred at a young school age.

The purpose of the study- to develop the speed of physical activity based on the method of rotational training in physical education classes of primary school children.

Given the sensitive period in the development of motor speed in the main part of the lesson, the use of the rotational training method with the targeted use of exercises aimed at improving this quality can significantly increase the level of motor development in young school-age children.

Organization of pedagogical practice. Secondary school No. 29 in Karshi, Kashkadarya region, was selected for the experiment. A pedagogical experiment (67 8-9-year-old primary school students) was conducted to determine the effectiveness of the developed method of developing motor activity speed with young school-age children. Classes in the control group were conducted with a physical education

teacher according to the traditional physical education program. In the experimental group, in the main part of the lesson, the students performed specific exercises of a certain size for 8-10 minutes. The method developed included four sets of exercises (15 seconds each) using a rotational exercise method, with a rest interval of 30 seconds between them and 1 minute between exercise series. Duration of this method - 2 lessons per week for a total of 8 weeks.

The cycle set included the following exercises (Table 1.2):

1) Running for 30m (from a high start with a command signal, speed qualities, reactivity were assessed, three attempts were made, the best result is taken into account);

2) Running to 60m (from a high start, speed qualities were evaluated, three attempts were made, the best result is taken into account);

3) Jumping up (Abalakov method, assessment of speed and strength qualities, full adjustment of the body by jumping up, three attempts are made, the best result is taken into account);

4) long jump (assessment of speed-power qualities; three attempts were made, the best result was taken into account);

5) jumping rope (on both legs, assessing speed qualities, the test taker tries to make as many jumps on both legs as possible for 15 seconds);

6) 3x10m sprint (assessment of the student's speed qualities, from the initial state of the forward high forward);

Prior to the experiment, students were screened and the following tests were used to determine and assess the level of development of motor speed:

1-table

The pedagogical experience is in the groups examined at the beginning

Comparative analysis of boys n = 41

T/r	Control standards	CG	EG	P
1.	30 m run, sec	6,7±0,21	6,5±0,11	<0,05
2.	60 m run, sec	11,2±0,24	11,7±0,28	<0,05

3.	Jump up (according to Abalakov), see	14,5±1,73	15,1±1,93	<0,05
4.	Long jump from place to place, cm	135,1±8,20	137,2±7,30	<0,05
5.	Jump rope (15 sec), times	9,24±1,7	10,1±1,6	<0,05
6.	3x10 shuttle running, sec	11,20±0,31	11,8±0,32	<0,05

2-table

**The pedagogical experience is in the groups examined at the beginning
Comparative analysis of girls n = 26**

T/p	Control standards	CG	EG	P
1.	30 m run, sec	6,9±0,23	6,7±0,17	<0,05
2.	60 m run, sec	11,7±0,28	10,9±0,20	<0,05
3.	Jump up (according to Abalakov), see	27,35±1,86	31,6±1,82	<0,05
4.	Long jump from place to place, cm	139±1,35	141±1,92	<0,05
5.	Jump rope (15 sec), times	11,2±1,7	12,1±1,3	<0,05
6.	3x10 shuttle running, sec	10,9±0,40	10,8±0,22	<0,05

Research results. After statistical analysis of the results, the effectiveness of the method developed in the development of speed of movement in young school-age children was demonstrated. According to him, before the start of the experiment, there were no differences in terms of physical fitness among the students of the control and experimental group ($R \geq 0.05$). Throughout the pedagogical experience, controls with young school-age children showed that motor activity (rotational training) was more effective than traditional training (3,4-). table). According to him, the average speed of running in 30 m in boys is 5.7 sec .; Running 60 m 9.7 sec. the results showed an improvement in girls of 5.9 and 9.8, respectively. We also observed that in the high jump, rope jumping, and moccasin running tests, the performance of female students was much better than that of male students, according to which the high jump was 19.6 in boys. cm was 33.6 cm in girls, long jump was 145.6 cm in boys, 148.6 cm in girls and 3x10 moccasin running test. boys showed a result of 10.6 sec and girls 9.8 sec. This, in turn, proves once again

that the physical fitness of 8-9-year-old schoolgirls is slightly better than that of boys.

3-table

**In the groups examined at the end of the pedagogical experiment
comparative analysis of boys = 41**

T/p	Control standards	CG	EG	P
1.	30 m run, sec	6,1±0,31	5,7±0,12	<0,05
2.	60 m run, sec	10,1±0,26	9,7±0,21	<0,05
3.	Jump up (according to Abalakov), see	17,1±1,36	19,6±1,87	<0,05
4.	Long jump from place to place, cm	140,3±7,17	145,6±6,42	<0,05
5.	Jump rope (15 sec), times	11±1,6	17±1,3	<0,05
6.	3x10 shuttle running, sec	10,9±0,36	10,6±0,28	<0,05

4-table

**In the groups examined at the end of the pedagogical experiment
Comparative analysis of girls' performance = 26**

T/p	Control standards	CG	EG	P
1.	30 m run, sec	5,9±0,24	5,8±0,20	<0,05
2.	60 m run, sec	10,3±0,28	9,8±0,17	<0,05
3.	Jump up (according to Abalakov), see	28,3±1,96	33,6±1,76	<0,05
4.	Long jump from place to place, cm	141,1±4,25	148,6±8,92	<0,05
5.	Jump rope (15 sec), times	14±1,4	15,1±1,6	<0,05
6.	3x10 shuttle running, sec	10,1±0,34	9,8±0,28	<0,05

Conclusion. The results of testing participants tested in pedagogical practice showed that the proposed method was much more effective than the program used in school practice, and confirmed that its use would be of great benefit to develop agility at a young school age.

According to him, the average speed of boys running 30 m is 5.7 seconds; Running 60 m 9.7 sec. the results showed an improvement in girls of 5.9 and 9.8, respectively. We also observed that in the high jump, rope jumping, and moccasin

running tests, the performance of female students was much better than that of male students, according to which the high jump was 19.6 in boys. cm was 33.6 cm in girls, long jump was 145.6 cm in boys, 148.6 cm in girls and 3x10 moksimon running test. boys showed a result of 10.6 sec and girls 9.8 sec. This, in turn, proves once again that the physical fitness of 8-9-year-old schoolgirls is slightly better than that of boys.

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